

table). The highest plant height was observed in T₂, where GA₃ was applied without flag leaf clipping. But the differences during the boro season were non-significant. The number of tillers and panicles per hill remained statistically identical among all treatments in both seasons. The outcrossing rate in the boro season was highest in T₄, where GA₃ and flag leaf clipping were done

simultaneously. The average outcrossing rate was also highest in T₄ in the T. aman season, but the differences were nonsignificant. The highest hybrid rice seed yield was observed in T₄, which was significantly higher than that of the control plots in the boro season. Differences in the T₂, T₃, and T₄ were nonsignificant. No significant differences were observed in terms of seed yield among differ-

ent treatments during T. aman.

It is concluded that hybrid rice seed yield was increased by the application of GA₃ and flag leaf clipping. Seed yield was lower in the T. aman season because of unfavorable weather conditions and pest infestations during the growth period in Gazipur, Bangladesh.

Rice yield as affected by use of biofortified straw compost combined with NPK fertilizer

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To fully exploit the yield potential of input-responsive, high-yielding rice cultivars, agronomists generally consider improving the management of essential macro mineral elements only (NPK) while ignoring the rest. Rice straw as farm waste was found useful for sustaining rice productivity and soil health in a pollution-free environment when used either alone or in combination with mineral fertilizers (macro- and micronutrients) or bioactivators or both (Gaur 1999). This study was conducted during the 2002 and 2003 rainy seasons at the BHU Research Farm to find the efficiency of bio-fortified rice straw compost in combination with NPK in transplanted rice.

Soil at the experimental site was sandy clay loam (Ustochrept) with a pH of 7.2 and an ECE of 0.33 dS m⁻¹ at 25 °C. It was moderately fertile, being low in organic C (0.46%) and available N (180 kg ha⁻¹) and medium in available P (19 kg ha⁻¹) and K (206 kg ha⁻¹). The experiment was carried out in a randomized

block design. Samba Mansuri (BPT5204) was the test crop used. Half the amount of N and full P and K were applied as basal; the remaining N was applied in two equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation. Rice straw compost was applied at 6 t ha⁻¹ before transplanting. To prepare this, rice straw was collected from the threshing floor and brought to the composting pit (3 m length × 2 m breadth × 1 m height). Rice straw was spread layer after layer, with each layer having a thickness of 15 cm. On each layer, urea solution (1 kg urea for 1,000 L of water) was spread. These pits (three in number) were irrigated frequently to maintain the moisture level at 80–100%. The rice straw compost was treated with a suitable culture of N₂-fixing bacteria (*Azotobacter chroococcum* to raise their number to 100 × 10⁶ 100 kg⁻¹ of organic material), P-solubilizing fungi (*Trichoderma viridae* at 300 g t⁻¹ of raw material), and PSB (*Bacillus polymyxa* at 500 g t⁻¹ of raw material) to obtain compost with enriched qual-

ity. Low-grade rock phosphate (1%) was added to improve the P content of the compost. Rice straw compost was enriched with spraying of salt solution containing 12 kg CaSO₄·2H₂O, 6 kg SSP, 4 kg MgSO₄, 500 g FeSO₄, 200 g ZnSO₄, 15 g MgCl₂, 7 g CuSO₄, 70 g H₃BO₃, 5 g (NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄·4H₂O, and 7 g CoSO₄. These salts were sufficient for approximately 1 t of composting biomass and were dissolved in 10 L of water and sprayed on the composting mass at the 30th day of the process. The material was thoroughly mixed three times at 15-d intervals during the entire composting period for proper aeration. The total decomposed rice straw compost thus obtained had a concentration of 0.43% N, 0.09% P, 1.16% K, 0.80% CaO, 0.02% Fe, and 3.82% Si.

The pooled grain and straw yield data (Table 1) were significantly influenced by the biofortified rice straw compost superimposed on NPK. Maximum yield was obtained with the application of rice straw compost inoculated

Table 1. Effect of treatments on grain yield, straw yield, and harvest index of transplanted rice (pooled over 2 y).

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Harvest index (%)
T ₁ (NPK + rice straw compost)	4.5	7.4	37.78
T ₂ (NPK + cellulocompost)	4.6	7.5	37.75
T ₃ (NPK + azocompost)	5.0	7.7	39.55
T ₄ (NPK + bacteriocompost)	5.1	7.9	39.24
T ₅ (NPK + cellulocompost + azocompost)	5.1	7.9	39.37
T ₆ (NPK + cellulocompost + bacteriocompost)	5.3	8.0	39.84
T ₇ (NPK + azocompost + bacteriocompost)	5.6	8.6	39.47
T ₈ (NPK + cellulocompost + azocompost + bacteriocompost)	5.4	8.1	39.80
T ₉ (NPK + enriched rice straw compost)	4.9	7.6	39.37
T ₁₀ (NPK only)	4.5	7.4	37.79
SEm ±	0.75	1.3	0.5
CD (P = 0.05)	2.14	3.7	1.4

Table 2. Interaction effect between treatment and year on grain yield of transplanted rice.

Treatment	Grain yield (kg ha ⁻¹)									
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	T ₆	T ₇	T ₈	T ₉	T ₁₀
Y ₁	40.67	41.87	49.07	49.97	51.37	53.73	55.73	55.23	48.13	41.67
Y ₂	49.17	49.60	50.83	51.27	51.67	52.13	56.67	52.50	50.43	47.93
	SEm ±						1.06			
	CD (P = 0.05)						3.03			

with azocompost + bacteriocompost along with NPK (T₇). The harvest index was also likewise

influenced. The efficient supply of nutrients delayed senescence and increased the life cycle of

the plant, which resulted in higher economic yield. Production of rice grain and straw was enhanced with the addition of rice straw compost, *Azotobacter*, and bacteriocompost as well as the integrated use of rice straw compost along with *Azotobacter* and PSB (Singh 2001). The interaction effects between years and treatments were statistically significant (Table 2). Treatments T₁, T₂, and T₁₀ resulted in a significant improvement in yield in the second year over the first year. However, the other treatments did not differ significantly due to years. The highest yield was recorded with T₇ in both years.

References

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Response of rice cv Pusa Basmati 1 to different planting methods

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In India, rice cultivation is becoming increasingly expensive as seedlings are raised in nurseries and transplanted manually. Rice transplanters are yet to be popularized. Manual transplanting alone accounts for nearly 20% of the total cultivation cost. In most cases, the required plant population is not maintained because laborers are not properly supervised as transplanting is done on a contractual basis. Manual transplanting takes lon-

ger to complete. Therefore, major constraints are the high cost of manual transplanting and uneven plant population. Our experiment was designed to explore other options for rice crop establishment during the 2000-03 rainy seasons (July-October).

Rice seedlings were raised in a wetbed nursery. Direct drilling and broadcasting of pregerminated seeds of rice were also done in puddle-leveled rice plots on the same day seeds were sown

in the nursery to maintain the same seedling age for all treatments. Seed bolls were prepared by mixing fresh cow dung, wood ash, and clay soil (1:1:2 ratio), adding four seeds in each boll, and drying them completely. Seed bolls were dibbled in rows under puddled conditions on the same day seeds were sown in the nursery. Twenty-one-day-old seedlings were transplanted at two to three seedlings per hill at the same spacing as that of drill-